

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ENSURING FIRE SAFETY AND EVACUATION OF POPULATION GROUPS WITH LOW MOBILITY FROM SHOPPING AND ENTERTAINMENT CENTERS: CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS

Dotsenko O.,

Institute of Public Administration and Research in Civil Protection

(Fire and emergency modeling department of the fire protection research center, Senior Research Fellow)

Borysova A.

Institute of Public Administration and Research in Civil Protection

(Sector of Editorial and Scientific-Publishing Activity, head of the sector),

PhD, Senior Researcher

Abstract

Analysis and research of safety and evacuation in shopping and entertainment centers is an important direction in research on fire safety and emergency situations. The article examines the current state of development of shopping and entertainment centers in Ukraine and the world. The statistics of fires in shopping and entertainment centers were analyzed: the statistical data on fires in such centers were studied, which are key to assessing risks and determining priority directions for improving fire safety. The current state of fire safety measures is analyzed, namely the available research and measures aimed at increasing the level of fire safety in shopping and entertainment centers. The requirements for evacuation routes and exits have been considered. The study of the evacuation of mixed flows of people of different mobility groups during evacuation is analyzed, which is a difficult task for the development of effective strategies and program solutions.

Keywords: shopping and entertainment center, fire safety, evacuation of people, few mobile groups.

1 Introduction

The modern stage of urban development is characterized by a rapid increase in the number of objects with a large number of people, which creates complex challenges in terms of ensuring safety in them, especially for low-mobility population groups. Shopping and entertainment centers (TCCs) are becoming one of the most actively visited places in cities, and their complex planning structure and large area create great challenges for fire safety.

The appearance of a significant number of visitors with disabilities in shopping malls causes the need to study and solve issues related to their safety and evacuation in case of emergency situations, such as fire. Injury risks are higher for these population groups, which underscores the importance of developing effective strategies and standards for their protection.

Despite the progress in mall evacuation research, there are shortcomings in standards and documentation that do not take into account the diversity of people's flows and their mobility. This creates gaps in the development of effective evacuation plans, especially in situations of mixed flows of people of different mobility groups.

In this regard, the scientific community expresses the need to conduct further research on evacuation from shopping malls, taking into account the needs of less mobile population groups and developing standards that take into account the diversity of participants in evacuation flows. This will be an important step in ensuring the safety and protection of all citizens in emergency situations and will contribute to the creation of a more accessible environment for all city dwellers.

The study of fire safety in shopping and entertainment centers covers various aspects, including the current state of their development both in Ukraine

and in the world. Analyzing fire statistics helps to understand risks and prioritize safety improvements. The study of the current state of fire safety measures and requirements for evacuation routes and exits takes into account the peculiarities of the less mobile population groups. Evacuation processes, in particular mixed flows of people of different mobility groups, are studied to develop effective strategies and program solutions. The analysis of existing software complexes is aimed at improving evacuation time calculations and is based on scientific research.

2. Research methods. The research uses a comprehensive approach, which includes the analysis and generalization of modern scientific and technical achievements in the field of studying the processes of evacuation of people of different mobility groups from buildings with a mass presence of people.

3. Presenting main material

In connection with the world processes of integration and globalization, new types of public spaces have appeared in Ukraine since the beginning of the 21st century, in particular, shopping and entertainment centers. These objects have become one of the most popular formats of public spaces due to their convenient location, multifunctionality and variety of services. Shopping and entertainment centers are a collection of shops and entertainment facilities, united by pedestrian alleys, and usually have an attractive design and parking lots. In global practice, there are various classifications of shopping centers that take into account such criteria as size, target market, configuration of premises and composition of tenants.

One of the main classification criteria is the zone of influence, which divides the centers into micro-district, district, district and regional centers. There are also classifications by size, tenant type, and physical

characteristics. Shopping and entertainment centers have become an important element of the Ukrainian and global retail industry, but there is no unified classification of these objects in Ukraine. The popularity of shopping malls requires focusing attention on ensuring their fire safety and developing appropriate standards.

Each shopping and entertainment center aims to provide a full range of cultural and entertainment services. Therefore, cinemas, children's playrooms, and billiard bowling clubs are additionally located in such institutions. Ice rinks, art galleries or a water park are a little less common in shopping and entertainment centers, which is caused by the requirements for more available space for their placement.

According to [1], the fire safety of the facility must be ensured by the following systems:

- fire prevention system;
- fire protection complex;
- the facility's fire safety management system.

These systems should be characterized by the level of ensuring fire safety of people (preventing the impact of dangerous fire factors on them) and material values, as well as economic criteria of cost effectiveness for its provision, taking into account all stages (scientific development, design, construction, operation) of the life cycle of objects and perform one of the following tasks:

- minimize the probability of fire;
- to ensure people's fire safety;
- to ensure fire safety of material values;
- to ensure fire safety of people and material values at the same time.

Objects must have fire safety systems aimed at preventing people from being exposed to dangerous fire factors, in particular their secondary manifestations at the required level.

The acceptable level of fire safety of people at the facilities should be no less than 0.99999 per year per person, and the acceptable level of individual fire risk should be no more than 10-5 per year per person.

According to statistical data [2] In 2023, there were 611 fires (-32.2%) in the buildings of trade and food facilities, which is 22.5% of the total number of fires at the facilities.

A significant number of researchers around the world are engaged in research on the topic of fire safety in shopping and entertainment centers, and research is also carried out by domestic scientists [3], which indicates a great interest in this issue both at the international and national levels. The results of these studies provide important conclusions and recommendations for improving safety systems and preventing possible negative consequences of fires in shopping malls.

The international community is actively studying the issue of fire safety in shopping and entertainment centers due to their complex structure, large number of visitors and specifics of functioning. These studies help identify risks, develop effective fire prevention and response strategies in these facilities.

Nowadays, the main regulators in the field of fire safety of trade and entertainment establishments are a number of normative documents, in particular DBN V.1.1-7:2016 "Fire safety of construction objects. General requirements", DBN V.2.2-23:2009 "Buildings

and structures. Trade enterprises" (Amendment No. 1), DBN V.2.2-9:2018 "Buildings and structures. Public buildings and structures. Basic provisions" (Amendment No. 1), DBN V.2.5-56:2014 "Fire protection systems protection" (Amendment No. 1) and others.

In their report [4], Dutch researchers emphasize the influence of the location of public buildings on the number of fires, whether they are isolated or connected to other structures. Thus, in the case of detached public buildings, the number of fires in a three-year period amounted to 65 cases. The opposite situation was observed in blocked shopping centers, where there were 91 fires during the same period, indicating a significant effect of such a connection with other buildings on the number of fires. According to this report, the increase in the number of fires for blocked shopping centers is 40%.

Statistics for five years [5] indicate that an average of 299 people are injured in fires in US commercial establishments every year, while 12 people die.

In the study [6], an analysis of fire statistics in Bangladesh was carried out, as a result of which it was found that the number of fires increased fivefold during 20 years. In 2019, at least 4,057 fires were linked to malls and markets, about 17% of the total number of fires in the same year.

Summarizing the above, it can be noted that there is a relationship between the occurrence of fires, their size, material damage, loss of human life and neglect of fire safety requirements.

During the analysis of scientific sources, it is worth noting that insufficient attention is paid to the study of the process of removing combustion products, taking into account their smoke-forming ability and mass rate of combustion. The design does not sufficiently take into account the fire load, as well as the linear speed of flame spread in the premises of shopping and entertainment centers of various purposes, and as a result, it is difficult to predict the safe evacuation of people.

A practically unexplored direction is the use of the possibilities of video surveillance located in shopping and entertainment establishments, as one of the elements of the fire alarm system and a type of monitoring of the evacuation of residents who belong to low-mobility population groups.

Conclusion

Normative documents relating to the arrangement of evacuation routes and exits in shopping malls, taking into account the presence of people with reduced mobility among visitors, determine important standards of safety and accessibility for all categories of people. According to these regulations, evacuation routes should be wide, spacious and meet safety requirements for people with different levels of mobility. Analysis of studies on the evacuation of mixed flows of people of different mobility groups shows the importance of understanding and taking into account different levels of mobility when designing and planning evacuation systems. Scientific studies indicate that taking into account the specifics of the movement of different groups of people, such as the disabled, the elderly, pregnant

women and others, is an important component of an effective evacuation system.

In particular, it was found that ensuring the availability of evacuation routes, equipment with ramps and other means for the movement of persons with disabilities plays a key role in ensuring their safety and evacuation efficiency. Research also emphasizes the need for the development of technologies and infrastructure that take into account the needs of different mobility groups, including the use of modern video surveillance systems and other technologies to improve the safety and efficiency of evacuation processes.

The generalization of research results indicates the importance of considering differentiated approaches to evacuation depending on mobility levels, which can contribute to improving overall safety and reducing risks in emergency situations.

This wide range of research demonstrates the seriousness of fire safety issues in malls and determines the importance of further efforts in improving fire prevention measures and technologies to ensure the safety of visitors and employees of these facilities.

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